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“Edukasyon Ipadayon, Pagtudlo Kanunayng Palamboon”

The key to life is Education. Education is the most powerful weapon we can use to change the world according to Nelson Mandela, as he has proven it right and was the country's first black head of state in South Africa. Over the past two years, the Philippine Educational System has been challenged when there was the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak. The pandemic has brought a lot of abrupt changes in our educational system. The past School years come with new modes of learning which we called the “New Normal”. At first, I wondered. Where do we start? How do we start this New Normal thing in Education? How do we face academic challenges in the New Normal of Education? Have you asked these questions in your mind as well?

We are beset by different challenges in the New Normal of Education. As we look back on the fruitful and productive years that we had, a lot of challenges have come our way in producing such proficient, effective, and globally competitive learners in the entire country as well. More than 28 million students have enrolled for School Year (SY) 2022-2023. Yes, you heard it right - 28 million students. Wow! It is a very large number of students, right? Administrators, teachers, stakeholders, and even students have a lot of things in mind.

First, what are the so-called teaching strategies that teachers need to employ with these large numbers of enrolled students? Was there a learning loss in the previous years due to the different learning modalities? Those are questions that we need to ponder. Teaching is the noblest profession. Why? Because it takes courage and passion to be a teacher. Teachers do not just teach they inspire students as well. Teachers made all professions possible. There will be no engineers who build buildings and bridges without teachers, no doctors who cure sick people without teachers, no policemen who secure safety and security without teachers, no lawyers who defend everybody's rights without teachers, no sailors and pilots who transport goods and passengers without teachers, no bankers who secure people's money without teachers, no IT specialists who develop software systems without teachers and etcetera. It is only evident that teachers used varied teaching strategies to make all professions possible.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, these teaching strategies have been challenged by a lot of learning modalities being used for our dear students to make sure that the best quality education has been given to them. There are different learning modalities in the New Normal in Education namely: Modular printed and digital copy, Online Distance learning, Radio and television, and Blended learning. Yet, we embraced the said challenges wholeheartedly with open arms to take a new step to be good, better, and best until the good becomes better, and the better becomes best.

Second, caused by these different learning modalities, what are the struggles faced by our students, teachers as well as by our parents? The educational system and institutions are affected by economic and social issues badly as classroom activities are stopped due to nationwide closure. Some struggles are prolonged physical isolation which led to depression and anxiety, the use of technology tools that are new both to parents, teachers, and students, and the adjustment of the different learning modalities being used. All of us have been adjusting to the New Normal in Education we have right now. Change has been so abrupt. But wait, every beginning has its own ending. This School Year gives us that so-called Change.

Yesterday, as I stare at the sunset, it reminded me that everything has come to an end and that endings are not a bad thing. In fact, with endings come new beginnings. And this school year gives us a new beginning since the full face-to-face has been fully implemented and educational challenges have been addressed.

After all, the greatest glory in accepting the challenges in this New Normal in Education lies not in never falling, but in rising every time we fall, and we must focus to see the light during our darkest moments. Finally, the support of our beloved stakeholders has been our torch of light as we hold hands and hands and together let us reach our goals for the betterment of the of the entire country.

Teachers let us be the change maker of today. There are only a few people who are born great teachers but all of us could at least become good teachers, but we do not settle for less, because we would like to settle for the best. According to Dr. Bongo, our Schools Division Superintendent, Love your work, if you love your work, you will be happy.

